

Analysis of Requirements for a Cyber Physical Production System in the Automotive Industry

Full Paper

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Abstract

This paper reports on a Systems Analysis task for specifying the business requirements of a leading automotive industry manufacturer for augmenting their production system with cyber physical components to address two problems that they are currently facing with inbound logistics and production interruptions both of which could result in substantial financial losses. Requirements were captured, documented and reasoned about using a systematic approach that was facilitated by a conceptual modeling framework, consisting of 4 modeling views, for iteratively representing information gathered from domain experts and for validating the requirements.

Keywords

Systems Analysis, Production Systems, Cyber Physical Production Systems, Automotive Industry, Capability Oriented Requirements Engineering.

Introduction

Traditional manufacturing and production systems are in the throes of a digital transformation. By blending the real and virtual production world, it is now possible to connect all parts of the production process: devices, products, systems and people. A term that has come to represent this transformation is that of Industry 4.0 (Deloitte 2016). More specifically to production systems, terms that have come to dominate the debate are those of Factory of the Future (FoF) and Cyber Physical Production Systems (CPPS) (IEC 2016).

In this context many manufacturing companies are considering possible ways of transforming their current production environments towards those that are underpinned by ICT-related capabilities that will offer them a greater degree of connectivity, monitoring, analyzing, simulating, optimizing and controlling production entities and processes. This paper reports on a Systems Analysis project for the Fiat Chrysler Corporation, henceforth referred to as FCA, in specifying their requirements for transforming key parts of their production towards CPPS capabilities. This work was carried out as part of the [DISRUPT](#) project.

The aim of FCA is to have the necessary components and capability to produce without interruption. By enabling design, monitoring and reconfiguration of the supply chain, FCA wishes to be able to quickly set-up and adapt the manufacturing conditions to changing conditions, whether related to incoming events in manufacturing, transportation, or even at higher tiers in the supply chain where usually the company does not have visibility.

Problem Context & Motivation

FCA is one of the largest automotive manufacturers in the world, with multiple production sites in several countries. One of the main production processes is automobile assembly from a number of components (chassis, engine and gearbox, suspension, fuel tank, wheels, seats, glasses and doors, etc.). The delivery and assembly of components are highly automated using automatic guided vehicles and robotic arms.

Since automobiles are made to order, only small stocks of components are kept in the warehouse. Assembly is based on JIS (Just in Sequence) delivery of components which allows for a sequencing system for parts in which when the body arrives to the station, the respective parts, chosen by the customer, also arrive at the station, to be assembled by the operator. Therefore, smooth supply of the necessary components is essential.

The whole process is supported by a number of software systems. In particular, the sequence is computed in the Order Slotting and Sequencing System (OSS) taking into account a number of parameters including the components to be built in-house, the sourced components, and the plant availability and capacity. Once computed the sequence is sent automatically to an internal software tool (RTM), where the bill of materials (BOM) is residing. From RTM the sequence is forwarded to the Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and to the Material Requirements Planning System (MRP) for the material requirements planning and subsequent forwarding to the suppliers.

The production planning and scheduling has been automated to a satisfactory degree according to the capabilities of the current software configuration. However, FCA still faces problems when there is a disruption in either inbound logistics or production interruptions. The main obstacles that can generate bottlenecks in the supply network are stock-outs and changes in the delivery of components causing problems with the car units produced per person hour (Jobs per Hour), which incur heavy costs for the manufacturer. As the production cycle time is fixed throughout the line, alternative production sequences or transportation modes should be devised in order to retain the capability to produce without interruption.

Against this problem backdrop a project that sought to capture the business requirements, often referred to as *early requirements* (Fuxman et al. 2003; Loucopoulos 2004) was carried out to identify the set of new capabilities in order for FCA to be able to satisfactorily deal with these problems.

Capability Oriented Requirements Engineering (CORE)

The process

The approach adopted, known as CORE involved three main activities of ‘information gathering’, ‘conceptual modeling’ and ‘stakeholder reviewing’. These activities were carried out in an iterative manner resulting in a stepwise refinement of the results being produced.

Information gathering refers to the collection of information relating to the user case using a number of instruments (online forms, structures elicitation forms, collaborative workshops, onsite visits). It results in textual description of the existing enterprise situation, as well as the user needs and aspirations with respect to the foreseen functionality and quality of the new system under development.

The use of natural language has the advantage of ease of transferability but falls short on formality that in turn hinders any potential analysis that one might apply on such knowledge in order to inform decision makers on appropriate strategies. The use of conceptual modeling languages overcomes these shortcomings.

The *conceptual modeling* framework applied in CORE is based on recent work (Loucopoulos 2016; Loucopoulos and Kavakli 2016a; Loucopoulos and Kavakli 2016b). It employs a set of complimentary and intertwined modeling paradigms based on enterprise *capabilities, goals, actors, and information objects*.

It should be noted that the conceptual models do not simply constitute more formal representations of the information gathered in the corresponding elicitation forms. Rather, they are developed through the creative analysis (transformational, exploratory, combinatorial) of gathered information, by exploring captured assumptions, suggesting new concepts, refinements of and/or new connections between documented concepts and evaluating the effectiveness of elicited ideas.

This normally results in additional and/or revised information about the modeled domain, which then progresses with a new round of activities of modeling and reviewing. Therefore, *stakeholders’ reviewing* is an essential component of the RE process carried out during both information gathering and conceptual modeling in face-to-face meetings, workshops and teleconferencing sessions of requirements

modelers with user representatives until a consensus is reached that the models are correct in relation to the current AS-IS situation and the user requirements are properly represented.

The models

The CORE framework considers 4 interrelated viewpoints, each one being facilitated by a distinct conceptual modeling perspective, whilst ensuring that consistency is achieved across all four, through appropriate inter-model interactions.

The **capability** model focuses on the capacities and abilities necessary for a particular application. Capability is a higher-level concept that gives us the opportunity to consider the essential elements on which the enterprise functions, without having to consider how this functioning comes about. Capability is defined by the Open Management Group as the abilities and capacities that the business may possess or exchange to achieve certain outcome (OMG 2013). The Department of Defense Architecture Framework (DODAF) defines capability as the ability to achieve a desired effect under specified (performance) standards and conditions through combinations of ways and means (activities and resources) to perform a set of activities (DoD 2008). The NATO Architecture Framework (NAF) defines capability as the ability of one or more resources to deliver a specified type of effect or a specified course of action (MoD 2013).

The **goal** model focuses on enterprise's objectives for retaining, acquiring or developing the necessary capabilities for the application. Goal Oriented Requirements Engineering (GORE) has long been established as a strong method to identifying and analyzing the intentionality of stakeholders (Horkoff et al. 2012; Yu and Mylopoulos 1998) Goal-oriented approaches such as the Knowledge Acquisition in automated Specification (KAOS) method (Lamsweerde 2001), *i** (Yu 1993) and Enterprise Knowledge Development (EKD) (Kavakli and Loucopoulos 1999) state that enterprises are purposefully designed and implemented systems. A goal model describes the 'causal transformation' of strategic goals into one or more sub-goals that constitute the means of achieving desired ends. Each step can result in the identification of new goals that are linked to the original one through causal relations thus forming a hierarchy of goals. Related to business goals are a number of quality requirements (referred to as soft goals), e.g. production line efficiency or production process effectiveness. These soft goals motivate the analysis for discovering the KPIs that affect the operationalization of related goals and provide the basis for evaluating or revising current enterprise behavior.

The **actor-dependency** model focuses on the socio-technical components of the enterprise that relate to specific capabilities for the application. Actor-oriented approaches such as the Intentional Strategic Actor Relationships modeling (*i**) framework (Yu 1995; Yu and Mylopoulos 1994), or Role-Activity modeling (Ould 2005) are based on the premise that enterprises are social systems and therefore, the essence of an enterprise's operation lies in the interaction between involved social agents. Such approaches provide opportunities for modeling enterprise processes at a sufficiently high level of abstraction, which is particularly relevant and useful at the early requirements phase of any project.

The **informational** model focuses on the logical structure of the informational resources that are part of the enterprise's capabilities and act as the medium of communication between enterprise actors when they are trying to meet specific enterprise goals.

The 4 different types of modeling represent the dimension of abstraction being applied. Orthogonal to this is the dimension of requirements lifecycle, which is a set of phases for progressing from an existing situation to a new desired situation. The relationship between abstraction and lifecycle with details of what is involved at each intersection is provided in Table 1.

Change goals provide a way of identifying and reasoning about the requirements for change from an intentional perspective together with their KPIs. Reasoning about change goals is based on the premise that the desired changes (whether they reflect radical business re-design or incremental improvements) are derived through the comparison of the 'desired' vision against the 'present' reality (the current goal model).

Rather than prescribing a solution based on experts' assumptions, this process aims to *re-interpret each change requirement in relation to the existing enterprise goals*. The result of this activity is the

construction of a revised goal model (the Change Goal Model) detailing how stakeholders' requirements for change may be realized.

Abstractions <i>Lifecycle</i>	Enterprise Capabilities (Capability Modeling)	Enterprise Motivation (Goal Modeling)	Enterprise Functioning (Actor-dependency Modeling)	Enterprise Information (Informational Modeling)
Enterprise AS-IS	Capacities & Abilities	Existing Goals & KPIs	Actors & dependencies	Information Objects
Enterprise Requirements		Change Goals & New KPIs		

Table 1. Modeling abstractions in the context of requirements definition lifecycle

There is a close synergy between the 4 types of model and this synergy has essentially two advantages. First, during the iterations of models, requirements engineers can refine the models by examining the influences of the concepts in one model on the others. For example, in the actor model we can define dependencies on informational resources. On identifying this dependency one can ensure that the informational resource is also present in the informational model. Second, when models are being reviewed, requirements engineers can verify the information contained in the models by examining that all concepts in all models are those that are necessary and sufficient. For example, if in the actor model there is an informational object and that is not presented in the informational model, then it is evident that either of the models is not complete, which in turn will trigger further investigation and re-modeling. Figure 1 shows a high level view of the basic elements of the four modeling views and their relationships.

Figure 1. Inter-model relationships

The Application of CORE on the FCA Application

In the current situation at FCA, addressing non-availability of components (recovery action) is based on the expertise of the human actor responsible for the logistics of the plant. Any recovery action (e.g. select another transporter, or reschedule production plan) should take into consideration a number of constraints such as the stability of production sequence, saturation of plant capacity, saturation of resources, maximization of throughput (JPH), minimization of stock.

Modeling the AS-IS situation

Business capabilities

The FCA the AS-IS capability model defines 5 main capabilities denoted in the model shown in Figure 2 as *Inbound Logistics*, *Material Management*, *Production Planning*, *Production Scheduling* and *Production*.

Figure 2. FCA current business capabilities

These capabilities exist because of certain assets that the company possesses and the ability in the form of means or skills inherent in these assets. For example, **Material Management** is a capability of FCA that deploys assets such as the **Warehouse / Dock Station Manager** in collaboration with the **MES** and **WMS** software, having the knowledge, expertise and software ability for **Monitoring** and **Configuring**. In the model of Figure 2 capacities and abilities are indicated for each capability.

The functionality of the chosen use application is possible because FCA are the owner of capabilities **CAP1-CAP5** as well as because of the collaboration between these capabilities. For example, **Production Scheduling** which is deployed on a daily basis, collaborates with both **Material Management**, in order to determine the supply of required materials, and also with **Production Planning**, in order to ascertain the level of commitment for medium to long term production intentions.

Capabilities **CAP1-CAP5** are considered as internal capabilities, i.e. they are fully owned by FCA and therefore are in a position to review, and update their configuration of capabilities. In the new situation such a re-configuration will need to take place in order for FCA to utilize CPPS capabilities.

In addition to these internal capabilities, there are two external capabilities that are owned by enterprises with which FCA collaborate but whose capabilities are not owned, controlled or subject to any influence by FCA, at least in the current business model. These are capabilities **CAP6** and **CAP7**. They are included in the capability model in order to externalize these relationships, which may be very significant if in the TO-BE situation there may be opportunities for a closer collaboration of FCA with external entities for example suppliers and logistics companies, perhaps making use of IoT functionalities.

The model of Figure 2 provides the scoping for the FCA application. It acts as an anchor point for the rest of the models, which will use this model for answering: “why does the enterprise need these capabilities?” (answered by the goal model), “what socio-technical actors are involved and how do they co-operate in order to meet these enterprise goals?” (answered by the actor dependency model), and “what kind of information is used in this co-operation?” (answered by the informational object model). Therefore, this capability model represents a high-level of abstraction in identifying the key levers of current operation in this specific application of FCA. If FCA needs to meet some other new goals (which will be detailed in the

change goals model) then one would need to answer the questions of “which one of these ‘levers’ need to change?”, the answer to which will lead to a new TO-BE situation.

Business Goals

The goal hierarchy depicted in Figure 3 is a fraction of the overall goal model for FCA. It illustrates the operationalization of goal *G1.To manage disruptions in supply network*. As shown in this figure, *G1*, is initially refined in two sub-goals, namely *G1.1.To detect events originating from the supply network w.r.t. critical components* and *G1.2.To react to events originating from the supply network w.r.t. critical components*. These are in turn decomposed into a number of operational goals, which are finally assigned to specific enterprise agents (in this case human actors). For example, *G1.1.3.To monitor material handling at docking stations* is assigned to the *Warehouse/Docking Station Manager*, whilst *G1.1.2.To monitor transportation plan* is assigned to the *Logistics Team*. It should be noted that these actors had already been identified as resources (capacities) and documented in the capability model.

Figure 3. Operationalization of “G1. To manage disruptions in supply network”

Related to *G1* is the soft goal *G1.3.Efficient disruption management*. Soft goals are often characterized by subjectivity, in the sense that there is no clear-cut, or agreed a-priori, criterion about what constitutes the achievement of that goal. The utility of soft goals is in motivating the analysis for discovering the KPIs that affect the operationalization of related goals and provide the basis for evaluating or revising the identified business capabilities.

For example, the analysis of soft goal *G1.3* resulted in the identification of a number of relevant KPIs including, the *No of events detected*, *Delivery lead-time*, *Handling lead-time*, *Time to generate recovery plan*, *No of stock-out*, etc.

Business Actors and Dependencies

The goal model described in the previous section gives an intentional description of the FCA case. By associating business goals to specific actors the reasoning for retaining them as enterprise capacities is

modeling the dependencies of actors, and specifically those that require resource collaboration where the resource is informational then it is possible to identify components of the informational model. On the other hand, when focusing on the informational model, relationships between the objects may reveal an actor dependency, which means that the actor-dependency model will need to be revised and refined. Given that this model represents the current informational capabilities of FCA, the new system configuration will need to examine this capability and to design and implement a new TO-BE situation that uses the best features of this and revises it to exploit new IoT and CPPS features.

The key informational objects for the current FCA situation are shown in Figure 5. As can be seen in Figure 5, the main informational object is that of **EVENT**. An event can be classified as **PROCESS QUALITY EVENT**, **MAINTENANCE EVENT** **MATERIAL EVENT**, associated to the **JOB SEQUENCE**, the status of some **EQUIPMENT**, or the availability or quality of some **MATERIAL**, respectively. As a reaction to some event a **RECOVERY PLAN** is generated which may affect the **MATERIAL REQUIREMENTS PLAN**, the associated **TRANSPORTATION PLAN** or the **PRODUCTION PLAN**.

Figure 5. The FCA informational objects

Modeling the Business Goals for Change – FCA Requirements for CPPS

Change goals express FCA’s needs and wishes as well as perceived opportunities with respect to the CPPS technologies. The hierarchy of change goals was constructed in a top down manner, step by step, by generating the change goals either as *improvements* of the current goals or by *introducing* new goals. This process iterates on three main activities: (i) Determine the impact of perceived ‘automation’ on current business goals; (ii) Modify the current goal hierarchy to reflect these changes; and (iii) Re-assign operational goals to existing or foreseen actors (the CPPS components).

The result of this process, illustrated in Figure 6, is a change goal hierarchy corresponding to goal **G1. To manage disruptions in supply network (improve)**. Due to space limitations, the change goal model shown in Figure 6 is but a small fraction of the overall change goal model for this application. Many of these system goals replace existing current goals, previously assigned to specific human actors. For example, change goal **G1.1.1. To automate monitoring of the delivery of components from suppliers (introduce)** assigned to the **CPPS - Complex Event Processing Module**, replaces the current goal **G1.1.1. To monitor delivery of components from suppliers** currently assigned to the **Logistics Team**. Thus, it becomes obvious that the improvement sought by FCA will affect the dependencies between current actors and the associated capabilities. On the other

hand, goal **GI.1.4. To automate anticipation of events (introduce)** is a completely new addition to the current goal hierarchy motivated by the new system.

Also, in the case of change goals, special attention was given to the identification of associated *soft goals*, as these will be used for the identification of the (possibly) new KPIs against which any new development will be measured. For example, the analysis of soft goal **GI.1.9. Increase no of anticipated events** resulted in the identification of the following new KPIs **Number of events anticipated**, **Time for event anticipation** and **Number of disruptions**. In the change goals model in Figure 6, each business goal for change has at least one KPI associated with it (shown as soft goals).

Figure 6. Correspondence between AS-IS and Change operational FCA Goals

Thus, through this analysis it is possible to provide a clear *causality analysis* between FCA requirements and expected CPPS functionality. This causality works in both directions. It is possible to provide a rational justification for the CPPS system components based on tracing high-level enterprise goals to CPPS system components. Alternatively, it is possible to trace the reasoning from desired CPPS system components to enterprise goals.

Conclusions

The area of requirements in which the work of this task falls is that of *early requirements*, i.e. requirements that are enterprise facing as opposed to *late requirements* that concern system functionalities. The CORE approach engaged user stakeholders and requirements engineers in information gathering, conceptual modeling and stakeholders' reviewing. The result of adopting a systematic and systemic approach involving these 3 main process activities, resulted in a set of models, that are cross-referenced so that a decision maker can trace causalities between current capabilities to desired ones through an analysis of enterprise goals, enterprise actors and enterprise informational resources.

On the basis of this analysis FCA have been in a position to design the architecture for a CPPS that considers the key modules as defined in the change goal models and justified in terms of their juxtaposing against the current FCA business goals and their capabilities.

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